

EFFECTS OF PROCESSING CONDITIONS IN UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER THERMOPLASTIC TAPE LAYING

D. Tanabe¹, K. Nishiyabu² and T. Kurashiki¹

¹Department of Management of Industry and technology, Osaka University
2-1 Yamadaoka, Suita 565-0871, Osaka, Japan

Email: d-tanabe@mit.eng.osaka-u.ac.jp, web page: <https://www.osaka-u.ac.jp/en/index.html>

²Department of Mechanical Engineering, Kindai University
3-4-1 Kowakae, Higashiosaka 577-8502, Osaka, Japan

Email: nishiyabu@mech.kindai.ac.jp, web page: <http://www.kindai.ac.jp>

Keywords: ATL, CF/PA6, Near-infrared heater, Heating behaviour, Single lap joint, Shear strength

ABSTRACT

Automated thermoplastic tape laying (ATL) and automated fiber placement (AFP) are high-potential manufacturing methods for continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites which can ensure operational safety even in highly loaded components such as aircraft wing skins and fuselages or construction large scaled structures. These methods often use computer-controlled robotics to lay one or several layers of carbon fiber thermoplastic tape or tows onto a mold, and should be optimized some processing parameters such as heating, pressing and feed speed and so on. Though the final aim of this study is to manufacture composite laminates made from tapes pre-impregnated with unidirectional carbon fiber reinforcement and a thermoplastic matrix, this study focuses on thermal distribution and interlaminar bond strength in a laying process of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic tape. The tape are commonly heated up to the melting temperature by various heating sources including heated roller, hot gas torch, near-infrared light lamp, induction coil and high power diode laser and so on. A near-infrared heater has some advantages such as rapid start-up speed, suitable for heating of carbon fiber and low cost. However, the heating characteristic is deeply influenced by position of the heater and feed rate of prepreg tape, thus it is necessary to optimize these heating parameters. On the other hand, the crystallinity of thermoplastic polymers is directly affected by cooling rate, and the bonding strength between prepreg tapes is depended on the degree of crystallization. Therefore, it is important for the thermoplastic prepreg tape laying process to investigate the cooling and consolidation behavior. This study aimed to predict the optimum processing condition for thermoplastic tape laying. The material used for the experiment was unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced polyamide 6 prepreg tape. The effects of processing conditions such as number and position of infrared heaters, feed speed of tape, temperature and pressure of compaction roller on the laying behavior of prepreg tape were investigated. The temperature distribution on the prepreg tape obtained by infrared thermometer and thermocouple measurement and the interlaminar shear strength of tapes are correlated as concluding remarks of this study.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic (cFRTP) composites which can be manufactured with press-forming are attracting attention recently in aircraft and automobile applications. However, cFRTP components have rather simple geometry due to the limited deformation allowed for the reinforcing fibers and high viscosity of the resin, and thus require joining as an indispensable step in the manufacturing process of cFRTP. Moreover, the demand of on-site joining without facilities is also expected for a large-scale cFRTP structures. Also lots of waste materials were generally generated by trimming in preforming step for press-forming of cFRTP. This procedure is undesirable from the viewpoints of ecology and economics. Also the discontinuous fiber reinforced thermoplastics after trimming do not have sufficient mechanical properties for applications in primary structural components. Therefore continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic products ensure

high reliability in strength in highly loaded components such as aircraft wing skins and fuselages or construction large scaled structures [1].

To develop this type of primary structural components, automated thermoplastic tape laying (ATL) or automated fiber placement (AFP) are the key technologies in manufacturing of cFRTP products. These methods often use computer-controlled robotics to lay one or several layers of carbon fiber thermoplastic tape or tows onto a mold. The tape or tows are commonly heated up to the melting temperature by various heating sources including heated roller, hot gas torch, near-infrared light lamp, induction coil and high powder diode laser and so on. A near-infrared heater has some advantages such as rapid start-up speed, suitable for heating of carbon fiber and low cost. On the other hand, the crystallinity of thermoplastic polymers is directly affected by cooling rate, and the joining strength between prepreg tapes is depended on the degree of crystallization. Therefore, it is important for the thermoplastic prepreg tape laying process to investigate the cooling and consolidation behavior. However, the heating characteristic is deeply influenced by position of the heater and feed rate of prepreg tape, thus it is necessary to optimize these heating parameters. However the thermal fusion bonding mechanism has not ever been studied in details, and also the processing parameters such as heating, pressing and feed speed and so on has not been clarified at this moment [1, 2].

This study focused on thermal distribution and interlaminar shear strength in a laying process of unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic tape to predict the optimum processing condition for carbon fiber prepreg tape laying. The effects of processing conditions such as the position of infrared heaters, feed speed of tape, temperature and pressure of compaction roller on the laying behavior of prepreg tape and their bonding strength were investigated.

2 EXPERIMENTAL MATERIAL AND PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

The materials used for the experiment is unidirectional CF/PA6 prepreg sheet (TenCate, CETEX[®] TC910). This laminate has 5H sateen weave construction with a resin content of $V_f=58\text{vol.}\%$ and a thickness of $t=0.16\text{mm}$. The PA6 resin is semi-crystalline polymer. The result of differential scanning calorimeter (DSC) analysis shown that the glass-transition temperature is $T_g=50^\circ\text{C}$, and the melting temperature is $T_m=225^\circ\text{C}$.

Figure 1: Scan images of unidirectional CF/PA6 prepreg sheet.

2.2 Lamination process

Figure 2 shows appearance of the tape laying machine which has been manufactured for the basic experiments originally by authors. The near-infrared heater (Heraeus, ZKB600/80G) was used as source of heating. The heater which has two tungsten filament as heating source is suitable as the heater of CFRTP prepreg tape because the absorbed fraction is high into black body as carbon fiber. The consolidation rollers are heated rapidly to any temperature by an induction heating equipment (Hidec Co., Ltd.). This tape laying process is divided into the three steps. Firstly, the prepreg sheets are heated by near infrared heater. Then, the matrix polymer of prepreg sheets is melted rapidly. Secondly, two prepreg tapes are welded by pressing using consolidation rollers. Finally, the laminated tape is cooled down.

Two fine thermocouple (ANBE SMT Co., Ltd., KSG-40-100-100, type K) were bonded on the surface of prepreg tape to investigate the fusion bonding behavior. Two prepreg tapes with 50mm in width were inserted to consolidation roller at an angle of $\theta_{CF}=60^\circ$. The fiber direction of two prepreg tapes and the feed direction is same direction. The angle of the near-infrared heater was fixed at $\theta_H=30^\circ$, and the feed speed was changed from $v=14\text{mm/s}$ from to $v=28\text{mm/s}$.

Figure 2: Appearance of ATL machine.

2.3 Evaluation method

The heating behavior of the surface of prepreg tape was measured by fine wire thermocouples using a temperature measuring instrument (Graphtech Co., Ltd., midi LOGGER GL200A). The images of joint surfaces peeled off after joining were imported with a scanner device (Epson Co., Ltd., ES-7000H). The welding surfaces were also observed with a microscope to investigate the state of fusion bonding. The single lap tensile shear strength (LSS) test was carried out to evaluate a joint strength by using universal testing machine (SHIMAZU Co., Ltd., AG-50kN XDplus). Figure 3 shows the appearance of single lap tensile shear strength test specimen. Before LSS testing, aluminum tabs were bonded to end of specimens with epoxy adhesive. The cross-head speed was $v=0.5\text{mm/min}$. The LSS was calculated by using equation:

$$\tau_{ap} = \frac{P}{A_L} \quad (1)$$

where τ , lap shear strength [MPa]; A_L , overlap area [mm] and P , maximum tensile force [N].

Figure 3: Geometry of single lap tensile shear strength test specimens.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Effects of distance of near infrared heater

Figure 4 shows the change of surface temperature of CF/PA6 prepreg tape at $v=14\text{mm/s}$. The temperature of pressure roller was $T_R=30^\circ\text{C}$. The temperature of prepreg tapes were increased with increasing the x -coordinate. When the prepreg tapes were cooled down quickly, the tapes were contacted to the pressure roller. The area of contact between upper prepreg tape and the pressure roller was larger than that of lower prepreg tape. Also, when the distance of heater was $x_H=50\text{mm}$ and $x_H=60\text{mm}$, the temperature was reached over $T=225^\circ\text{C}$ which is close to the melting temperature of PA6 polymer. The maximum temperature was increased with decreasing the distance between heater and pressure rollers (x_H). It was also revealed that the range of heating was increased with decreasing the distance of heater. From these results, it is considered that the proper distance of the heater is from 50mm to 60mm.

Figure 4: Change of surface temperature of CF/PA6 prepreg tape at $v=14\text{mm/s}$.

3.2 Effects of feed speed

The feed speed of prepreg tapes was changed to investigate the effects of the feed speed of prepreg tape on the heating behaviour as shown in Figure 5. Figure 5 shows the change of surface temperature of CF/PA6 prepreg tape at $v=28\text{mm/s}$. The temperature of pressure roller was $T_R=30^\circ\text{C}$. The maximum temperature was increased with decreasing the distance of near infrared heater (x_H). When the distance of near infrared heater was $x_H=50\text{mm}$, the surface temperature was achieved over $T=190^\circ\text{C}$ at both surfaces. It was revealed that the maximum temperature and the rate of temperature increase were decreased compared to the result of $v=14\text{mm/s}$.

Figure 5: Change of surface temperature of CF/PA6 prepreg tape at $v=28$ mm/s.

3.3 Single lap shear strength

Figure 6 shows the result of single lap shear strength test. The lap shear strength (τ_{ap}) and the maximum load (P_{max}) were increased with decreasing the distance between heater and pressure roller (x_H). The feed speed was $v=14$ mm/s, the lap shear strength and maximum load were higher than $v=28$ mm/s because the matrix polymer of prepreg tapes melted sufficiently. From these results, it was considered that the lap shear strength was improved with decreasing the feed speed. However, it is necessary to attend the high temperature oxidation of the matrix polymer and the reduction of productivity.

Figure 6: Result of single lap shear strength test of CF/PA6 laminated tapes.

3.4 Microscopic observation

Figure 7 shows the result of microscopic observation of peeling surface of laminated prepreg tape at $v=14\text{mm/s}$ and $v=28\text{mm/s}$. In the case of $v=14\text{mm/s}$ and $x_H=40\text{mm}$, pores of varied sizes were seen remarkably on the peeling surfaces. It was considered that these pores were attributable to moisture in the prepreg tapes. When the laminated condition was $v=14\text{mm/s}$ and $x_H=50 - 60\text{mm}$, the peeling of carbon fibers was seen totally because the prepreg tapes were laminated soundly. In the case of $v=28\text{mm/s}$ and $x_H=40\text{mm}$, the peeling of carbon fibers was also seen remarkably. When the laminated condition was $v=28\text{mm/s}$ and $x_H=50\text{mm}$, the fracture surface was shown a similar trend compared to the laminated condition of $v=14\text{mm/s}$ and $x_H=70\text{mm}$. On the other hand, in the case of $v=28\text{mm/s}$ and $x_H=60 - 70\text{mm}$, the polymer rich layer was observed totally, because the temperature of prepreg tapes was lower than the melting temperature of PA6 polymer.

From these experimental facts, it was revealed that the fracture surface condition was depended on the position of near infrared heater and the feed speed of prepreg tapes. However, it is necessary to carry out the thermal analysis in order to investigate the crystallinity degree of matrix polymer.

Feed speed, v	Distance between heater and pressing roller, x_H			
	40mm	50mm	60mm	70mm
14mm/s				
28mm/s	<p>Polymer rich</p>			

Figure 7: Microscopic observation of peeling surface of laminated prepreg tape.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, the effects of processing condition for carbon fiber thermoplastic tape laying using near infrared heater was investigated to predict the optimum processing conditions. The heating behavior of prepreg tape was revealed by investigating the laminated condition such as the position of near infrared heater and the feed speed of prepreg tapes. The result of investigation of the effects of the position of near infrared heater on the surface temperature of prepreg tapes, it was revealed that the range of heating was increased with decreasing the distance of heater. From these results, it is considered that the proper distance of the heater is from 50mm to 60mm. From the result of single lap tensile shear strength test, it was considered that the lap shear strength was improved with decreasing the feed speed. However, it is necessary to attend the high temperature oxidation of the matrix polymer and the reduction of productivity. From the result of the microscopic observation of peeling surface of laminated prepreg tape, it was also revealed that the fracture surface condition was depended on the position of near infrared heater and the feed speed of prepreg tapes. For the future, it is necessary to carry out the thermal analysis in order to reveal the crystallinity degree of the matrix polymer of laminated tapes.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Grant-in-Aid for JKA RingRing Project Number 26-119 from a public interest incorporated foundation JKA in 2014.

REFERENCES

- [1] C.M. Stokes-Griffin, P. Compston, A combined optical-thermal model for near-infrared laser heating of thermoplastic composites in an automated tape placement process, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, In Press, Corrected Proof, Available online 14 August 2014.
- [2] Z. Qureshi, T. Swait, R. Scaife, H.M. El-Dessouky, In situ consolidation of thermoplastic prepreg tape using automated tape placement technology: Potential and possibilities, *Composites: Part B* 66 (2014) 255–267.